

CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF CONFLICTS AMONG STAFF AND MANAGEMENT OF COLLEGE OF HEALTH SCIENCE AND MANAGEMENT RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examines the causes of conflicts in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Port Harcourt and to ascertain the effects of the conflicts Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were used to guide the study. The study population is the entire staff of Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology, Port Harcourt both teaching and non-teaching staff. A simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred and sixty-five (165) staff from the population. The instrument for data collection is the Effect and Cause of Conflict Questionnaire (ECCQ) prepared by the researcher. Split-half was used to establish the reliability index 0.81. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent t-test. From the results, it was concluded that there is no significant difference between perceptions of teaching and non-teaching staffs on the cause and effects of conflict in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology Port Harcourt. The study also concluded that there is no significant difference between perceptions of teaching and non-teaching staffs on the types of conflict in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology, Port Harcourt. Based on the finding, it was recommended that there should be adequate conflict and resolution management mechanism in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology Port Harcourt to reduce conflicts and enhance productivity in the college. It was also recommended that there should be effective communication channel and adequate human relation in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology Port Harcourt to create room for negotiation as at when necessary.